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The Impact of Using English Curriculum Design Based on Industry Needs in English Teaching on Vocational School to Improve Students English Skill for Industry Standard Working Communication

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Abstract

The output of vocational school (VS) still has lower competence in English communication for industrial working. It made Industry owners reject out of VS graduates to work on their companies. This research presents the result of implementing the English Curriculum Based on Industry Needs (ECBIN) in vocational schools. Following Nargers Rasidi (2016) this research uses questioners to find the perception of students and industry to ECBIN. Students and industry perception also is collected by interviews to 36 students and 5 managers of Industry who uses vocational output as workers. To find out the impact of implementing ECBIN on vocational school to the stents skill, this research conducted experimental activity. The result of research shows that the first is the competence of students after treatment ECBIN, students' competence increased by average of speaking score 75.58, listening 72.65, reading 80.34 and writing 78.56 for average. The score of students before treatment is 65.30 for speaking, 54.35 for listening, 70.12 for reading and 60.45 for writing skills. Secondly, it is found that students perception of ECBIN shows positive significantly 65,45 % agree and 11,57% students strongly agree. Thirdly, Industries stated 61,11% agree and 17,60 % strongly agree that ECBIN is very useful to support the output of vocational school for their career. So it can be concluded that English Curriculum based on industry or work field is more effective and useful for students and also companies. Vocational schools in Indonesia should change English curriculum from general English to English for Specific Purpose (ESP).

Keywords: English Curriculum-Based Industry Needs (ECBIN), English Students Skill, English for Industrial Standard, Vocational School

1. Introduction

Curriculum of English in vocational schools of Indonesia is still far from the expectation because it is held without need Analysis. Vocational school output is designed to be the candidate of workers who will be ready work directly in industries. They must be part of industries. Industry development is very fast. It is caused by Asians Nations

that makes agreement Economy ASEAN Community. This agreement cannot be thought as simple thing by vocational school. In it, the competition of working, business, capital dan power of country will be happened and it can be stopped. One of the most important is language for communication. It had been pointed that language for communication is English. So teaching English in vocational school must be different with senior high school. Vocational school has its own targets. But in many vocational schools in Indonesia, teaching English is still in general curriculum. They do not aware of the Economy ASEAN Community needs analysis. So it is important to investigate fit English teaching curriculum for Vocational schools.

2. Literature Review

Vocational school needs innovative curriculum to prepare the output in order to have competitive skill in English communication. Teaching English must accommodate skill for real conditions where the output of vocational school work. The English for specific needs is one of choice to motivate students in learning English to prepare their future in working. The ESP such as English for working or business is interesting to apply in learning and teaching English. Prachanant (2012), Pinelopi (2015), and Li (2016), Zahedpisheh N and Saffari N (2017), and Farrell, T. S. C., & Bennis, K. (2013) in their research about the use of English for Specific purposes shows that ESP is more effective to improve skill and motivation. They discuss that the research shows that it can explore students skill more. It shows that ESP is more effective for vocational school. Because of the condition of teaching and curriculum in vocational schools in Indonesia, it is important to design a curriculum for solving English skill students of vocational school problems. This is in line with Ahmed (2014), Alkhatib (2005), Baghban (2011) Basturkment (2010) Borgi & Anna (2005), Basthomi Y (2016) Fiorito L (2005), Hutchinson, T and Watter (1992), Kitkauskienne L (2006), Leong AM and Li J (2006), Liu. W and Huang Y (2013), Masaumpanah, Z and Tahririan M H (2013), Pham H L and Malvetti (2012), Dja'far, V. H., Cahyono, B. Y., & Bashtomi, Y. (2016). They discuss about teaching English for Specific Purpose (ESP). It can be understood that teaching English by using suitable curriculum related to the purpose give better result.

The innovation of learning and teaching English can be started by the designing of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs. As Ricards J.C (2001), Yin R.K (2009), Esteban, S. G., & Martínez, C. T. (2014) and Safnil (2019) discuss about the important of curriculum development in teaching English. Nasihin (2019) conducted research about teaching English for motorcycle technique students which results show that English material contained technical language is more effective to increase students motivation and skill. Suitable curriculum or model of learning is very important to make sure in reaching learning goal. As Nasihin, A, et.al. (2021) said that suitable method such as GBA in writing class can solve big problem of low skill in writing. So it is predicted that by suitable curriculum and learning design English skill of vocational school students can be improved.

This study was an attempt to answer research question: the firstly, how is competence of students in Vocational school after following learning activity by using curriculum designed based on industry communication needs; secondly how is the perception of students in Vocational school after following learning activity by using curriculum designed based on industry communication needs and thirdly, how is industry perception about learning and teaching English by using curriculum designed based on industry communication needs related to industry work.

3. Methods

Following Nargers Rasidi (2016) this study is used mix method. This research uses questioners to find the perception of students and the owners of industry to the design of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs on vocational school. Then, the impact of the curriculum is collected by pre-test and post-test. The participant of this research is 36 students of vocational school in business and management program of second year. From industry side, this research takes 6 industry owners to become the object of this study, they are Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI), astra honda Motor, Telkom Indonesia, Astra International Toyota, Astra International United Tractor and Sinetsu In Malaysia.

To find out the impact of implementing design of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs on vocational school to the students skill, this research conducted experimental activity. The students consist of 36 persons 31 female students and 5 male students. They followed English learning and teaching with materials such as; 1) Presenting proposal of the job in industry or company; 2) Presenting report of a job or project which has finished; 3) Presenting and responding manual book of operating tools; 3) Responding instruction of oral or sound based on the field study or work information; 4) Responding instruction of written form about work activities; 5) Writing Business letter and report of Job. At the end of semester, they followed test to know the improvement of skills in using English in communication.

The perception also is collected from interviews with 36 students of vocational school in second years. The perception of learning and teaching English by using curriculum designed based on industry communication takes from 6 managers of Industry who uses vocational output as workers at their company. According to Ary, D., Jacobs, Lucy, C., Sorensen, C., & Razavieh, A. (2010), the questionnaire must be scored, so the score as strongly agree (5), agree (4), not sure (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1) according to Ary, D., Jacobs, Lucy, C., Sorensen, C., & Razavieh, A. (2010).

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Findings

The question in this study was how competence of students in Vocational school after following learning activity by using curriculum designed based on industry communication needs (ECBIN). Then the second question was to find out the perception of students in Vocational school after following learning activity by using ECBIN. The third objective is to find out the industry perception about learning and teaching English by using ECBIN related to industry work.

The result of research shows that the firstly the competence of students after treatment design of ECBIN on vocational school increase by an average of speaking score 75,58, listening 72,65, reading 80, 34 and writing 78,56 for average. The score of students before treatment is 65, 30 for speaking, 54,35 for listening, 70,12 for reading and 60,45 for writing skills. The better achievement of students skills such as in industrial communication necessary which consists of stating planning or presentation in speaking and writing skill, receiving instruction in reading and listening comprehension skill and reporting job in speaking and writing skill.

Table 1: The changes score of student skill test before and after implementing ECBIN on vocational school

Kind of skill in communication	Score		Gap of score	Improvement percentage
	Before	After		
Speaking (Presentation, stating report and giving instruction)	65, 30	75,58	10,28	15,74%
Listening to presentation, reporting and receiving instruction	54,35	72,65	18,30	33, 67 %
Reading paper or letter of business, factual report of work and manual book of working.	70,12	80, 34	10, 22	14,58%
Writing letter, report and instruction of work or SOP.	60,45	78,56	18,11	29,96%

Table 2: Responses of students to ECBIN on vocational school in learning.

Questions/items	Frequency & Percent	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Not Sure	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Q1. English curriculum consists of industry communication needs based on vocational school is interesting	Fre	2	7	2	20	5	36
	Per	5,56	19,44	5,56	55,56	13,89	100

Q.2. The class activity of speaking, listening, reading and writing by Curriculum based industry communication needs on vocational school is useful for my future.	Fre	0	3	2	24	7	36
	Per	0	8,33	5,56	66,67	19,44	100
Q.3. I can speak, listen, read and write English for working need after learning by Curriculum based industry communication needs on vocational school	Fre	1	2	7	23	3	36
	Per	2,78	5,56	19,44	63,89	8,33	100
Q.4. I have Confidence to speak, listen, read and write English about working in my field/ competence program	Fre	2	1	3	26	4	36
	Per	5,56	2,78	8,33	72,22	11,11	100
Q.5. I am sure I can pass selection of working test about English competence after I studied by Curriculum based Industry/ working communication needs on my school.	Fre	0	1	4	29	2	36
	Per	0	2,78	11,11	80,56	5,56	100
Q.6. Curriculum based Industry/ working communication needs in my school help me much to do my job.	Free	0	2	2	28	4	36
	Per	0	5,56	5,56	77,78	11,11	100

Secondly, it is found that students perception to the design of ECBIN in vocational school shows positive significantly 65,45 %. Students state that they agree that learning English by the design of ECBIN on vocational school is interesting and useful for their job. 11,57% students are strongly agree that this curriculum and learning development can give useful achievement for them. They also say that they think that the design has provoke their motivation to learn English to prepare their future

From interview, Tobing said : Learning English based on industry need is more interesting and it is easier than learning general English, I believed that this English is really benefit for getting work” (Interview: June 2018). Other student, Dery Ervian said: by following this class I believe that this English is helpful in my future, so this motivation supported me to be competent in speaking, listening, reading and writing English about working in my field/ competence program” (Interview: June 2018)

Table 3: The perception of industry toward curriculum and learning by using ECBIN

Questions	Frequency & Percent	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Not Sure	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Q1. English curriculum consist of industry communication needs based on vocational school is suitable for candidate of worker.	Fre	0	0	1	4	1	6
	Per	0	0	16,67	66,67	16,67	100
Q.2. The Materials of speaking, listening, reading and writing by Curriculum based industry communication needs on vocational school is useful for worker future in my company.	Fre	0	0	0	5	1	6
	Per	0	0	0	83,33	16,67	100
Q.3. Out Put from Vocational School can speak, listen, read and write English for working need after learning by Curriculum	Fre	0	0	0	4	2	6
	Per						100

based industry communication needs.		0	0	0	66,67	33,33	
Q.4. the graduating student From vocational School look confidence to speak, listen, read and write English in working activity on my company.	Fre	0	0	2	3	1	6
	Per	0	0	33,33	50,00	16,67	100
Q.5. the graduated students of vocational school can pass selection of working test about English competence after following learning by curriculum based Industry/ working communication needs.	Fre	0	1	0	4	1	6
	Per	0	16,67	0	66,67	16,67	100
Q.6. Teaching English by using curriculum based Industry/ working communication needs can help worker to finish work at industry.	Fre	0	1	3	30	2	
	Per	0	11,11	8,33	83,33	5,56	

Thirdly, there are six big companies state that suitable English curriculum as ECBIN on vocational school help the student to increase their career in their company. They are Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI), astra honda Motor, Telkom Indonesia, Astra International Toyota, Astra International United Tractor and Sinetsu In Malaysia. They concluded that 61,11% industry owner agreed that the design of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs on vocational school is very useful to support the output of vocational school for their career in Industry or job field. 17,60 % industry are strongly agree that this curriculum and learning development is suitable, useful, helpful, and probably accepted by industry.

From interview to Muhyudi from Astra said: “ English in Industry is very important, so if Vocational School prepare ESP for student based industry or their program needs, it will help them to get good job and good in career” (Interview: June 2018). Meki from Sinetsu said: By mastering English in working place or special English based their study program, the graduated of vocational school can get good position” (Interview: May 2018)

From the result above it can explained as follow the first as predicted, the design of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs in vocational school is effective to increase the English competence of vocational students in communication need in industry work. It can be seen from the average of students score in English test in communication as 76,78 compare with 62,56 from both scores the gap is 14, 23 with percentage average is 23,48%. Secondly, it is fit to the purpose of the developed curriculum of English teaching and learning based on the industry need communication that this curriculum can increase the positive motivation of students to master English before they come to the work situation. Thirdly, industry also shows positive perception to the curriculum. It is the purpose of curriculum development to make sure image of Industry to vocational output.

4.2. Discussion

The first, the improvement of students' skills by this implementation of design of English Curriculum based on industry communication needs in teaching and learning English on vocational school as discussed above add to previous finding of Prachanant (2012), Pinelopi (2015), dan Li (2016) they had found in their research that the using of English in tourism industry can explore students skill more. Nasihin (2019) also found that the using of learning media or material based vocational content had improved motivation and skill of motorcycle technics students in vocational school. Qin (2018) found in his research in vocational school English learning for speaking class that action research is a useful and practical way to propel the development of the oral English teaching in higher vocational education.

The skill of students were improved by ECBIN such as; the first, the presentation skill in speaking. Students were taught and trained to use every word, sentence pronunciation and speaking style in presenting a proposal of

industry activities. Secondly, understanding instruction in manual book or receipt in industry communication. The students were trained to do action in activity based on the standard operational procedures related to the activity in Industry. The instruction is in letter form, memos, announcements and manual book related to the industry need. Thirdly, the material is skill in taking information from oral source in work activity. In this setting, the students are invited to memorize vocabulary related to industry the student work then they are asked to present meeting communication. For this meeting some students are asked to be a leader or manager who gives information or instructions and the other becomes workers to give responds and do the instruction. This setting will show the skill of students in taking oral information.

Secondly, this curriculum can increase students motivation in learning English because is more interesting. It is in line with Xhaferi (2010) and Pham, H. L., & Malvetti, A. (2012) that ESP courses deal mostly with “language in context” rather than “language usage” (grammar rules or ways of structuring the language). English curriculum based on industry communication need is specifics construct based work situation communication. It is in line with the term ESP is defined as “goal oriented language learning” (Robinson, 1991). Hutchinson & Waters (1992) define ESP as an approach to language learning which is based on the learners’ needs. So by this curriculum students believed that English is useful for their future and career.

Thirdly, Industry had positive image and trust in ECBIN implementation on Vocational School for students skill when they come to work in industry. This finding confirm previous research by Prachanant (2012), Pinelopi (2015), and Li (2016), Zahedpisheh N and Saffari N (2017), and Farrell, T. S. C., & Bennis, K. (2013) in their research about the using of English for Specific purpose shows that ESP is more effective to improve skill and motivation. They discuss that the research shows that it can explore students skill more. So industry can give trust of Students’ English skill from Vocational school by implementation English for Specific purpose or ESP.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

The research of using the ECBIN in teaching and learning English on vocational school can be concluded that firstly, more focused English curriculum to the program in vocational school and based on industry or work field can improve student skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing in communication of working in industry. Secondly, students has improvement in motivation to learn English due to the ECBIN implementation. Thirdly, industry gives appreciation for implementing the ECBIN on vocational school to prepare students before work.

This study demonstrates that teaching English by using ECBIN in teaching and learning English on vocational school shows positive impact. It can be suggested that the positive impact is from the increasing of students ‘skill, students’ motivation and industry trust to vocational school. So, this curriculum can be applied to all vocational school by revision based on skill program in certain vocational school.

Then, the research about relevant method and materials teaching for vocational school English is still important to conduct. More researches can make this findings become more guaranteed for industry trust to output of vocational school. In addition, if all vocational school agreed to use ESP design based Industry necessary, industry will accept the output of vocational school. Actually, the output of vocational school must be designed become competent in skill, smart in problem solving or adult personality and good in communication. There is no job can be held well without good communication.

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